

CHOICE PROJECT

Additional file 5: Teachers' students' descriptive characteristics.

The tool has 3 sections (A, B, and C) to be filled by the selected teacher

Section A: School characteristics

1	School name	
2	Sub County	
3	School ownership (Public, Private)	
4	School location (Rural, Urban, Semi-urban)	
5	Computer/laptop for learning and teaching	
6	Projector for learning and teaching	
7	Total number of Form one streams	

Section B: Teacher characteristics

1	Teachers name	Subject
2	Sex (Female, Male)	
3	Years of experience as a secondary school teacher	
4	The main subject that you teach	
5	The average number of form one students that you teach	

Research teacher name:

Sign

Date

Teacher responsible name:

Sign

Date

School Principal name:

Sign

Date

Section C: Student characteristics (insert details for all students in the participating class)

	Student name	Admission number	Sex	Age	Overall national examination grade (KCPE)
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					
8					
9					
10					
11					
12					
13					
14					
15					

Research teacher name:

Sign

Date

Teacher responsible name:

Sign

Date

School Principal name:

Sign

Date